

CONTEMPORARY AGRICULTURE
SAVREMENA POLJOPRIVREDA

The Serbian Journal of Agricultural Sciences
Srpski časopis za poljoprivredne nauke

Vol. 64, No. 3 - 4, Pp. 169 - 173, 2015.

www.contagri.info
ISSN: 0350-1205 UDC: 63(497.1)(051)-"540.2"

UNIVERSITAS STUDIORUM
NEOPLANTENSIS
University of Novi Sad,
Serbia
1954
FACULTY OF AGRICULTURE
Published by
Faculty of Agriculture,
Novi Sad

Original scientific paper

UDC: 631.871

INFLUENCE OF ORGANIC FERTILIZERS ON GROWTH OF COCKSCOMB (*Celosia plumosa* (Voss) Burv.)

Emina MLADENović, Jelena ČUKANOVIĆ, Mirjana LJUBOJEVIĆ, Ivana SENTIĆ,
Nikolina KATIĆ, Nataša KRSTIĆ¹*

Summary: The work examined the influence of two organic fertilizers on growth and flowering of plumed cockscomb (*Celosia plumosa* (Voss) Burv.). Two commercially available organic fertilizers, 'Slavol' and 'Ecobooster 2' were used. Plants of plumed cockscomb were produced in polystyrene containers. The investigation was conducted in a field experiment laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replicate plants per treatment. During production fertilizers were applied in the prescribed dosage every seven days. The results showed that 'Slavol' had positive influence on plant high, leaf width and length and on flower characteristics.

Key words: *Celosia plumosa*, organic fertilizers, leaf and flower characteristics

INTRODUCTION

Increasing flower production was observed in Serbia, in past several years. Cockscomb (*Celosia plumosa* (Voss) Burv.) is flowering species commonly used on green areas, in pots, arrangements or as a dried flower. In some countries, cockscomb is used for nutrition. The plants of cockscomb prefer a fertile, moist soil with lots of organic matter. They grow best in full sun but will tolerate partial shade. The flowers can be dried. Cockscombs are grown one by one 20 to 25 cm apart, and reach a height of half a meter.

In recent years a new kind of fertilizers containing mineral and organic matter of different origin, appeared on the market. Many fertilizers may also include some biostimulators (various microorganisms and phytohormones). It was found that their application favorably affect the effective utilization of other nutrients. By the application of these organic formulas it is possible to omit the traditional fertilization, which decreases costs and simplifies the production. The application of organic fertilizers in addition to mineral nutrition, provided positive results in the microbial activity improvement in the soil. Furthermore, the nutrient availability and release rates from organic fertilizers are affected by many factors, including application timing and rate, microbial activity, soil temperature and moisture, substrate components, and the nature of the organic fertilizer (Rosen and Allan, 2007). It is critical and also a major challenge in organic fertilizer management to find methods to optimize synchrony between nutrient mineralization and crop demand (Treadwell et al., 2007).

¹Emina Mladenović, PhD, Assistant Professor, Jelena Čukanović, PhD, Teaching Assistant, Mirjana Ljubojević, PhD, Assistant Professor, Ivana Sentić, MSc, Teaching Assistant, Nikolina Katić, BS, Nataša Krstić, MSc, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture, 8 Dositiej Obradović Sq., 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia.

*Corresponding author: Jelena Čukanović, e-mail: cukanovicj@polj.uns.ac.rs, phone: +381 21 485 3322

Fertilizer 'Slavol' is fluent microbiological fertilizer and growth biostimulator that is certified for use in organic and traditional agricultural production. This product is free of chemical additives and has positive effects on plants, soil and the environment. It is used for foliar application. 'Slavol' contains bacteria that have been isolated from the root surface and multiplied in appropriate culture media. In the process of reproduction these bacteria produce auxin, as a secondary metabolic product which is completely natural, as is auxin synthesized by plants. It also contains nitrogen fixer-associative bacteria that fix nitrogen and fosfomineralizator-bacteria that decompose organic phosphorus compounds.

'Eco booster 2' is an organic biostimulator, and eco-fertilizer in liquid form, with no delaying period in its application, as it can be used together with plant pesticides. By the special technology of preparation it is enhanced with two active amino acids, fulvic and humic. 'Eco booster 2' contains basic nutrients, nitrogen (9%), phosphorus (1%) and potassium (4%), and other trace elements affordable in highpercentage (chelate form). It affects the plant strength, increases the vegetative organs weight, intensifies the color in flowering plants, accelerates rooting, increases the plant resistance to diseases and abiotic stress, and accelerates the nutrients transport and all metabolic processes in the plant.

Main differences between organic and inorganic fertilizers are the timing and rate of nutrient release. Nutrients in organic fertilizers are often not immediately available to plants after application. The organic forms of nutrients must be converted by soil microbes into inorganic forms before the plants can use them (Gaskell and Smith, 2007). Among all the nutrients required for plant growth and development, nitrogen (N) is often the most limiting factor. When organic fertilizer is added to a substrate, the organic N sources in organic fertilizer need to undergo through a mineralization process in which soil microbes convert organic N compounds into ammonium and a subsequent process that quickly oxidizes the ammonium to nitrate (Gaskell and Smith, 2007). Mineralization determines the rate and availability of mineral N to the plants; however, it is a highly variable process that is affected by many factors such as substrate temperature, moisture and microbial activity of soil and the nature of the organic matter (Kraus et al., 2000, Scagel, 2005).

The aim of this study was to determine the influence of two organic fertilizers on growth and flowering of cockscomb.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The trial was set in March of 2014. year. We used the seeds of Italian seed company 'Franchi Sementi' which were sown in a styrofoam containers. The advantage compared to the polystyrene foam plastic containers is that styrofoam containers retains heat better. The containers that were used had 104 planting holes. Containers were pre-filled with a 'Maki' substrate (Maki substrates, Serbia) which is composed from baltic peat, baltic peat dark, clean earthworm and micro-elements. The substrate is fine-grained, dark colored and odorless. Analysed substrate has a favorable pH=7 and contains affordable quantities of macroelements (N, P, K, Ca, Mg) and trace elements (Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, B).

Once the seeds were sown, the soil was watered by sprinklers water and covered with a plastic sheet for better moisture retention. Cover was removed after seed germination, which began after three days (Figure 6).

First no sedive plants were grown in the pots of Ø 9 cm, after which treatment with fertilizers started. Plants were divided into two treatments and control with no treatment, of 30 plants in each treatment. Application of 'Slavol' was carried over the soil by adding to the solution in concentration of 2% in 7 days interval, until the end of the growing season. Application of 'Eco booster 2' was also performed over the soil, adding to the solution in a concentration of 1% in 14 days interval, three times during the growing season.

The plants were monitored by plant growth and development. Measurements were performed in 5 days interval during the growing season. Measured characteristics included plant height, number of leaves per plant, leaf width and length, inflorescence length and the length of the root system. Plant growth index $[(\text{height} + \text{widest width} + \text{perpendicular width}) \div 3]$ and number of fully open flowers were also recorded. Plant height was measured from the substrate surface to the most apical meristem.

RESULTS

Results of morphological characterization showed that 'Slavol' and 'Eco booster 2' increased plant height, leaf length and width and root length. The increase in biomass was significant in comparison to the control plants and a second organic fertilizer 'Eco booster 2'. Average plant height was 37.5 cm, while root length averaged 16.5 cm. Significantly greater leaf area was observed in treatments with organic fertilizers, since the leaves were bigger (Table 1).

Table 1. Morphological characteristics of the treated and control cockscomb (*Celosia plumosa* (Voss) Burv) plants

Traits	Plant height (cm)	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf width (cm)	Number of leaves	Flower length (cm)	Root length (cm)
Tretmans						
Control	23	5.5	3	12	7.5	11
Slavol	37.5	7	3.5	12	7	16.5
Ekobooster 2	27	6.5	3.4	12	4.5	12.5

Correlation analysis shown in table 2, indicated significantly high values of correlation coefficients between the plant height and root system length ($r=0,99$), plant height and leaf length ($r=0,90$) and the leaf length and width ($r=0,98$). Effects of organic fertilizer ‘Slavol’ was positively reflected in an optimal and balanced growth of above ground and underground parts of the plant. This has contributed to the promotion of flowering and be substantially improve the quality of the flower.

Table 2. Correlations of morphological characteristics of tested plants

Variable	Leaf length	Leaf width	Flower length	Root length
Plant height	0,90*	0,83	0,09	0,99*
Leaf length		0,98*	0,34	0,90*
Leaf width			0,47	0,83
Flower length				0,10

*Marked values are statistically significant for $p < 0.05$

Figures 1 – 4 show the relationship between the most significant morphological characteristics of the treated cockscomb (*Celosia plumosa* (Voss) Burv) plants. The statistical analysis of data showed that the plant height was significantly influenced by presence of auxin in organic fertilizer ‘Slavol’. Maximum leaf length and width were achieved again in plants treated with ‘Slavol’, while control plants had the lowest values of leaf traits. Average leaf number was same for both treatments and for control.

Figure 1. Correlation between plant height and root length

Figure 2. Correlation between leaf length and leaf width

Figure 3. Correlation between leaf length and root length

Figure 4. Correlation between leaf width and root length

Organic fertilizer 'Slavol' showed good results for flower length and shape of flower. Plants treated with 'Slavol' had a more regular shape and expressive color compared to another plants. Considering that the plants treated with 'Slavol' had greater leaf width, leaf length and better developed root system, there was a significant increase in the length and size of the blossom (Figure 5 and 6).

Figure 5. and Figure 6. Differences in length and size of blossom

Organic fertilizers 'Slavol' and 'Ecobooster2' showed good results according to control plants, but 'Slavol' had better impact on investigated characteristics (Figure 7 and 8).

Figure 7. and Figure 8. Effect of organic fertilizer on height, root length and number of leaves in cockscomb (*Celosia plumosa* (Voss) Burv) plants

DISCUSSION

The results of Hanč et al. (2008) showed that organic fertilizers could substitute the conventionally used mineral fertilization. They can even increase the yields more than mineral fertilizers. These are in agreement with our results since organic fertilizer 'Slavol' showed best results on investigated traits in cockscomb (*C. plumosa*).

Significant influence of auxin on apical dominance was reflected in plant height, since treated plants were higher more than 10 cm in comparison with plants treated with 'Ecobooster 2' and control plants.

Investigations of Gaskell et al. (2000) and Zhao et al. (2009) showed that application of commercial organic fertilizers had better influence on growth, yields and quality of plants in comparison to conventionally grown crops.

Rosen and Allan (2007) referred that nutrient availability and release rates from organic fertilizers are affected by many factors, including application timing and rate, microbial activity, soil temperature and moisture, substrate components and the nature of the organic fertilizer. Also Treadwell et al. (2007) concluded that a major challenge in organic fertilizer management is to find methods to optimize synchrony between nutrient mineralization and crop demand. Different crops may respond differently to different organic fertilizers. Therefore, it is important to test any new fertilizers before incorporating them into their production practices.

CONCLUSION

Flower crop production in recent years has a significant place in the market of products with application in horticulture and landscape architecture. Increasing production requirements necessarily imply improvement of the quality of flowering species. The application of organic fertilizers, such as 'Slavol' and 'Ecobooster 2', in intensive production of annual flowering species, would significantly improve the quality and increase incomes.

This research points out positive affect of organic fertilizers application on the cockscomb (*Celosia plumosa* (Voss) Burve) plants. The results show that 'Slavol' had positive influence on plant high, leaf width and length and on flower characteristics. The increase in biomass was significant in comparison to the control plants and a second organic fertilizer 'Ecobooster 2'. Significantly greater leaf area was observed since the leaves were bigger. Slavol showed good results for flower length and shape of inflorescence. Plants treated with 'Slavol' had a more regular shape and expressive color compared to another plants.

Based on the stated results organic fertilizers 'Slavol' and 'Ecobooster 2' are two organic fertilizers whose application should take wider place in flowerer plants production.

REFERENCES

- GASKELL, M., SMITH, R.: Nitrogen sources for organic vegetable crops. Hort. Technology, 17: 431–441, 2007.
- GUIHONG, B., WILLIAM, B.E., JAMES M.S., ANTHONY L.: Witcher effects of organic and inorganic fertilizers on marigold growth and flowering. Hort. Science, 45:1373–1377, 2010.
- HANČ, A., TLUSTOŠ, P., SZÁKOVÁ, J., BALÍK, J.: The influence of organic fertilizers application on phosphorus and potassium bioavailability. Plant Soil Environ., 54 (6): 247–254, 2008.
- KRAUS, H.T., MIKKELSEN, R.L., WARREN, S.L.: Container substrate temperatures affect mineralization of composts. Hort. Science, 35: 16–18, 2000.
- ROSEN, C.J., ALLAN, D.L.: Exploring the benefits of organic nutrient sources for crop production and soil quality. Hort. Technology, 17: 422–430, 2007.
- SCAGEL, C.F.: Inoculation with ericoid mycorrhizal fungi alters fertilizer use of highbush blueberry cultivars. Hort. Science, 40:786–794, 2005.
- TREADWELL, D.D., HOCHMUTH, G.J., HOCHMUTH, R.C., SIMONNE, E.H., DAVIS, L.L., LAUGHLIN, W.L., LI, Y., OLCZYK, T., SPRENKEL, R.K., OSBORNE, L.S.: Nutrient management in organic greenhouse herb production: Where are we now? Hort. Technology, 17:461–466, 2007.
- ZHAO, X., NECHOLS, J.R., WILLIAMS, K.A., WANG, W., CAREY, E.E.: Comparison of phenolic acids in organically and conventionally grown pac choi (*Brassica rapa* L. *chinensis*) J. Sci. Food Agr., 89: 940–946, 2009.

UTICAJ ORGANSKIH ĐUBRIVA NA RAST PETLOVE KRESTE (*CELOSIA PLUMOSA* (VOSS) BURV.)

Emina MLADENOVIĆ, Jelena ČUKANOVIĆ*, Mirjana LJUBOJEVIĆ, Ivana SENTIĆ,
Nikolina KATIĆ, Nataša KRSTIĆ

Izvod: U radu je ispitan uticaj dva organska đubriva na rast i cvetanje petlove kreste (*Celosia plumosa* (Voss) Burv.). Korišćena su organska đubriva dostupna na tržištu, 'Slavol' i 'Ecobooster'. Biljke petlove kreste proizvedene su u kontejnerima od stiropora. Ogled je postavljen u poljskim uslovima, po blok sistemu, sa dva tretmana po tri ponavljanja. Tokom proizvodnje đubriva su promenjivana u propisanim dozama na svakih 7 dana. Rezultati su pokazali da je organsko đubrivo 'Slavol' imalo pozitivan uticaj na visinu biljaka, širinu i dužinu lista i karakteristike cveta petlove kreste.

Ključne reči: *Celosia plumosa*, organska đubriva, karakteristike lista i cveta.

Received / Primičen: 31.08.2015.

Accepted / Prihvaćen: 15.9.2015.